

Speculation of the Relationship of Spin to Rotational Invariance

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One may note that a constant momentum (say $p(x)$) implies that this value holds for all x points. This suggests invariance in x space. In quantum mechanics, however, there is a chunkiness present due to a wavelength $= \hbar/p$. This chunkiness breaks spatial invariance, but we argue that its roots appear in p proportional to $\Delta x / \Delta t$ already breaking it because Δx becomes $-\Delta x$ if one changes the direction of the x axis. If one tries to create a probability function linked to conservation of momentum and the notion that given p_1+p_2 vectors, any p_3+p_4 (vectors) such that $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ has the same probability, one would consider $\exp(i |p|)$. The absolute value, however, is inconvenient (one wishes to have continuous function) and so one may make Δx quadratic, leading to $\exp(i p \Delta x)$ which introduces chunkiness into x because spatial invariance is broken. One may then introduce a generator linked to the invariance which becomes an operator which yields p .

We argue that in a three dimensional problem for a constant magnitude of momentum, there is not simply translational invariance, but also rotational. Given the number equal to $p(x)p(x)+p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$, one may have any $p(x),p(y),p(z)$ vector with this modulus squared. This rotational invariance is not associated with usual angular momentum (although we discuss this case as well.) We argue that one must deal with rotational invariance even for a fixed p and this implies that this holds even if one has $(0,0,p_z)$. Thus, there is a rotational invariance about each axis linked with symmetry breaking because there are two directions in which to circle an axis.

Another way to consider the problem is to write: $p(x) e_i + p(y) e_j + p(z) e_k$, where e_i, e_j, e_k are orthonormal basis vectors. Then one has a standard vector from linear algebra. $e_i d/dx + e_j d/dy + e_k d/dz$, however, is not a standard vector from linear algebra because it has no length. The coefficients of the basis vectors are numbers in linear algebra, but d/dx_i are operators. Thus, as argued in previous notes, one needs to replace e_i with an operator. If d/dx_i , as an operator, introduces chunkiness into a problem, then we argue that the operator which replaces e_i , must also introduce chunkiness, i.e. not discreteness. This, then leads to a second chunkiness, ultimately associated with rotational invariance of the p vector.

As a result, by trying to replace vector dot products with an operator equation, one may argue for replacing numbers and basis vectors with operators, with each operator being linked to physical "chunkiness" in the problem. As a result, spin seems to emerge in this manner, at least in the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case. Furthermore, just as $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ is linked with conservation of momentum, spinors, e.g. $|+\rangle|-\rangle$ should be linked to the conservation of a quantity which may be detected. There is no parameter ϕ here, as one consider angular motion about each axis) and so one does not have physical rotation, but nevertheless one has some chunkiness due to rotational invariance of $p \cdot p$ and this suggests some kind of motion which might interact with a magnetic field if a particle is charged, as it does. As a result, an interaction with a 2-slit apparatus shows chunkiness in space, while an interaction with a magnetic field reveals chunkiness linked with some kind of angular motion. In the two slit case, the particle has probability to interact with both slits, while with a magnetic field in a certain direction, one has two bands, one for each possible chunkiness value for spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Why should one only have two

values? One may see that the operator needed in a $p \cdot p$ case is a 2×2 matrix, with the sz matrix having two eigenvalues. One can flip from one to the other.

The main idea seems to be that a certain chunkiness in eigenfunctions is introduced by operators which are linked to an invariance in space, whether it be translational or rotational. In particular, the operator linked with invariance has to distinguish some discreteness (or chunkiness) in a function in order to return a value. For example, $d/dx 1 = 0$, but 1 is a number (i.e. not dependent on x). It also shows no value of p . One requires $\exp(ipx)$, which has chunkiness in x , together with $-d/dx$ to return p which holds for all x , i.e. is invariant in x . Replacing e_i with an operator which turns out to be a 2×2 matrix leads to an unexpected chunkiness, i.e. spin, in addition to the chunkiness of the wavelength.

$\exp(ipx)$, i.e. Discreteness or Chunkiness in Space Emerging due to Probability

The chunkiness or discreteness of space, which seems to be a surprise since it does not appear in classical physics and breaks spatial invariance, appears in $\exp(ipx)$ (or more generally in $\exp(ip \cdot r)$). Thus, we wish to examine this function.

Classically, space is invariant. If one wishes to introduce a probability for free particles such that one has conservation of momentum in a two body collision, and:

$$p_1 + p_2 \text{ (vectors)} = p_3 + p_4 \text{ (vectors)} \quad ((1))$$

then, one might consider:

$$\exp(i |p|) \quad ((2))$$

For a free particle, there is no real probability weight and so one is forced to use a complex number of modulus 1. ((2)) has the same value for p and $-p$, which is required, but the absolute value is not convenient. One would prefer a continuous function. Given that:

$$p \text{ is proportional to } dx/dt \quad ((3))$$

dx may be positive or negative, while dt is positive. Thus, p is linked with a direction in space if it appears in linear form, e.g. ((1)). It must be linear to ensure that any p_1, p_2 pair matches any p_3, p_4 with ((1)), but probability must not depend on the sign of p . One might rewrite ((2)), in one dimension as:

$$\exp(i p \Delta(x) / |\Delta(x)|) \quad ((4))$$

((4)), however, also contains an absolute value and so is no better than ((2)). To remove the absolute value sign seems to lead to a drastic choice:

$$\exp(i p \Delta x) \quad ((5))$$

In other words, a second variable is introduced which keeps p linear, but allows for p and $-p$ with Δx and $-\Delta x$ to have the same probability value. This leads to a breaking of the invariance in space as there are now chunks, called wavelengths:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \hbar / p \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one starts with a specific invariance, in this case spatial invariance. There is a conserved quantity, p , but is linked with the breaking of spatial invariance in the sense that it has two distinct directions in one dimension. Spatial invariance means there is no sense of direction. One must remove the sense of direction, but retain a continuous function which is linear in p . This seems to involve introducing a new variable which also depends on the x -axis. Given that p is proportional to Δx , one may introduce Δx as the variable to have a quadratic form $(\Delta x)^2$. In order to establish some kind of spatial invariance, the probability function must be periodic, i.e. $\exp(i p x)$. Thus, the invariant space is broken into chunks of $\Delta x = \hbar / p$.

Before continuing, we note that for a p vector, there is a sense of rotation. If one had rotational motion, one would expect similar arguments as those presented above to hold. In fact, they do if L_z is the conserved quantity and ϕ the classically continuous variable. In such a case, conservation leads to chunks again, i.e.

$$\exp(i m \phi) \quad ((7))$$

((7)), however, is not spin. Is it possible that there are still effects of rotational symmetry for a fixed (constant) p vector?

Rotational Invariance Even for a Fixed p vector?

One may create the function $\exp(ipx)$ (or $\exp(i p \cdot r)$) without linking it to the equation:

$$-\hbar^2 \nabla^2 \psi + V \psi = E \psi \quad ((8))$$

We first wish to point out that there is rotational invariance in $p \cdot p$ in ((8)) even if p is linear. One does not have to have angular momentum in order to consider rotational invariance effects, we argue. This means that there should be rotational consideration even for $(0,0,pz)$.

$\exp(i p \cdot r)$ and ((8)) are somewhat independent statements. In particular, the p vector appears in both, but one is not forced to introduce an operator $-i\hbar \nabla$ which yields p when acting on $\exp(ipx)$. We do point out, however, that one may construct such an operator and it is necessarily associated with chunkiness in x , otherwise it would return 0 when acting on a function of p alone. The notion of the removal of the direction of x -axis (part of the notion of co-ordinate space) which is required for a probability to be invariant under such a change, leads to chunkiness in x , as x is a variable, while p is a constant.

Given that one may obtain p from an operator acting on $\exp(ipx)$, one may argue that if one is interested in a probability expression, one may write (()) in terms of operators acting on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

This now leads to an issue. ((8)) as it stands represents numbers, but $p \cdot p$ makes use of the linear algebraic notion of a vector, i.e numbers multiplied by orthonormal basis vectors e_i (e_x, e_y, e_z). Linear algebraic vectors are not operators multiplied by e_i vectors. This is not a problem if

$$p \cdot p \longrightarrow -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} - \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} \quad ((9))$$

The point is that: $-i\frac{d}{dx}$ acting on $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ yields $p_x \exp(ip \cdot r)$. The operator form exists at the linear p level. As a result, it seems that one should be able to write:

$$p \text{ vector} = p(x) e_x + p(y) e_y + p(z) e_z \longrightarrow s_x (-i\frac{d}{dx}) + s_y (-i\frac{d}{dy}) + s_z (-i\frac{d}{dz}) \quad ((10))$$

A vector (which represents a certain kind of entity) is replaced by an overall operator as we have argued in previous notes. This seems to be the idea behind Dirac's linearizing of ((8))

We note that even if one replaces $p \cdot p$ with $p(x)p(x)+p(y)p(y)+p(z)p(z)$, one is acknowledging the existence of the p vector.

One may then proceed to show, as is well known, that s_x, s_y, s_z are the 2x2 Pauli matrices. S_z has two eigenfunctions:

$$(1,0) \text{ and } (0,1) \text{ to account for two choices (which we explain below).} \quad ((11))$$

As a result, the operator picture again introduces symmetry breaking (rotational without usual angular momentum) and leads to chunkiness.

Rotational Arguments Alone

We argue that the above ideas may also be arrived at by strictly considering rotational invariance contained in $p \cdot p$. We go a step further, however, by suggesting that there is rotational invariance linked with each axis.

Like with translational invariance in the $\exp(ipx)$ case, we consider the possibility of having a conserved quantity linked with rotational invariance (but not angular momentum). If there is such a quantity, one again has the sense of two directions (like p and $-p$), but now clockwise and counterclockwise motion for each axis. This breaks rotational symmetry (just like $p, -p$ breaks spatial invariance). Seeing that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are probabilities for p and $-p$, one may postulate a conserved quantity linked with this breaking of symmetry, i.e a two value situation. This again leads to chunkiness as one has the two solutions, but in this case there is no a priori magnitude as in the case of $|p|$ and so really only has two eigenfunctions, i.e. probability expressions.

One may then proceed to create operators linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and a two choice system, i.e.

$$(1,0) \text{ and } (0,1) \quad ((12))$$

((12)) should be linked with:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad ((13))$$

This holds for one axis, i.e there is rotational invariance about the z axis for example, but one must also have the same situation for y and x and these operators should allow $\sum s_i p_i$ to yield:

$$\sum s_i p_i * \sum s_i p_i = \sum p_i p_i \quad ((13))$$

Thus, there is a new rotational symmetry linked with each axis which carries a chunkiness linked to the idea of rotation in two directions about a particular axis.

Spin appears in a similar manner to $\exp(ipx)$ by considering the breaking of a physical invariance and the introduction of chunkiness. This, in turn, is linked to a conserved quantity, and an operator which is associated with the chunkiness. In the case of a conserved p, chunkiness is wavelength = \hbar/p and the operator is $-i\hbar/dx$ which is associated with the invariance. In the case of spin, rotational invariance about each axis is present, but one may postulate a conserved quantity (z projection of spin) with a fixed magnitude, but two directions of motion which is then chunky (two choices) and linked to a 2x2 matrix (S_z of the Pauli matrix set).

There seems to exist an almost identical analogy between $\exp(ipx)$ and spin $\frac{1}{2}$ in terms of symmetry breaking.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classically there exist certain symmetries like translational and rotational. If one tries to introduce a probability based on momentum to account for the idea that given p_1+p_2 (vectors) and p_3+p_4 (vectors) such that $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ have the same probability, one has the problem of symmetry breaking. First, there is no real weight to a free particle, so one might propose $\exp(i|p|)$ because p and -p should yield the same probability. The absolute value sign is needed to deal with symmetry breaking of space, but one then does not have a continuous function. Given that p is proportional to $\Delta x / \Delta t$, one sees that Δx breaks spatial symmetry and might suggest creating a quadratic form which does not, i.e. $\exp(i p \Delta x)$. This, however, introduces chunkiness in space which signifies symmetry breaking (of spatial invariance). The chunkiness is measured by \hbar/p .

In a similar way, one could have physical rotation linked with rotational invariance. The above arguments would suggest a probability of $\exp(i \hbar m \phi)$ for the conserved quantity $L_x = \hbar m$.

The argument we make here is that one does not need to have physical rotation in a circle to have rotational invariance. For a fixed p vector, one has: $-E^2 = c^2 p \cdot p + m^2 c^4$. $P \cdot p$ demonstrates rotational invariance and we argue that one might consider rotational invariance about each axis. (In such a way, each axis becomes like a little co-ordinate system of its own.)

One may note that there is rotational symmetry breaking as one may move around an axis in two directions. Here there is no a priori magnitude as for p . Thus, one expects two vectors (1,0) and (0,1). These are eigenfunctions of S_z (the Pauli 2x2 s_z matrix). Similar matrices should exist for s_x and s_y and allow for orthogonality of axis, i.e.

$$P \cdot p \longrightarrow (s_x p_x + s_y p_y + s_z p_z) * (s_x p_x + s_y p_y + s_z p_z).$$

In the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case, spin seems to mimic the creation of $\exp(ipx)$ based on symmetry breaking and the notion of a conserved quantity. Overall, for $-EE = cc p \cdot p + momoccc$, one would introduce 4x4 matrices, given by Dirac, which deal with the overall equation and not just $p \cdot p$. We argue, however, that essential symmetry breaking ideas are already present in $p \cdot p$ and that the 4x4 matrices contain the 2x2 Pauli matrices.